
EMPIRICAL ESTIMATION OF COEFFICIENTS OF CUTTING FORCE PARAMETERS IN TURNING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an empirical approach to estimate the coefficients of cutting force in turning processes. Cutting forces play crucial role in machining, affecting tool life, surface finish and overall productivity. Accurate estimation of cutting force coefficients is essential for optimizing machining parameters. Using experimental data from turning operation on AISI 1045 (steel) a regression model was developed to predict cutting force coefficients. A design matrix was constructed by applying the CCD. Response Surface Methodology (RSM) in design expert software was used to run the regression model. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the significance of the model and its parameters. The results showed that cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut significantly influence cutting force. The result also revealed 8.68, 10.87 and 10.12 are the coefficients of cutting speed, feed rate and depth of cut respectively. Also, high R^2 value of 0.8337 of the plot of predicted and actual values indicates the model can accurately predict cutting force with low values of variance inflation factors (VIFs) between 1.0 – 1.02 (less than 10). The proposed empirical model provides a practical tool for cutting force coefficients, enabling machinists to optimize turning process parameters for improved efficiency and productivity.

Keywords: Empirical estimation, cutting force, turning process, feed rate, cutting speed, depth of cut, optimization.

INTRODUCTION

Metal machining is a manufacturing process that involves using machine tools to remove materials from a work piece, typically metals to produce a desired shape, size and finish. The process has a long history dating back to the early industrial revolution but here is a brief background [1].

The first machine tools were developed in the 18th century [2]. This includes lathes and drilling machines. The 19th century saw the introduction of steam power and later electrically enabled mass production in machining. The early 20th century saw the development of high speed tools and the introduction of numerical control (NC) machines and this revolutionized metal machining process. The mid-20th century witnessed the advent of Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines which further increased precision and automation in metal machining. The late 20th century saw the advancement in material science and Computer Aided Design (CAD) software which enabled the production of computer parts and gave rise to precision engineering [3].

Finally, the 21st century brought to us the development of additive manufacturing (3D printing) and advance machining technologies like laser and water jet cutting which have expanded the capabilities of metal machining.

Some common metal machining techniques include turning (rotating the work piece when cutting with a lathe, drilling (cutting holes with a drill bit), milling (removing material with a milling cutter), and grinding (abrasive material removal with a grinding wheel).

Turning is a fundamental machining process widely used in manufacturing to produce cylindrical parts [4]. Cutting force is a critical parameter in turning, as it affects tool life, surface finish and product quality [5]. Accurate estimation of cutting force is essential for optimizing the turning process, predicting tool wear, and improving product quality [6].

Hence, this study focuses on the development of a robust method for estimating cutting force coefficients in the turning process, with the goal of improving tool life, surface finish, and product quality.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials

Workpiece Material: The workpiece material used is steel (AISI 1045). This is a medium carbon steel with chemical composition of carbon (C) 0.45%, Manganese (Mn): 0.6 – 0.9%, Phosphorus (P): 0.04%, Sulphur (S): 0.05%, Silicon (Si): 0.1 – 0.3%, Chromium (Cr): 0.1 – 0.3%, Molybdenum (Mo): 0.1 – 0.3%) balance Fe. Its mechanical properties are Tensile strength: 565-700 Mpa, Yield strength: 310 – 450 Mpa, Elongation at break: 16-22%, Hardness: 170-220HB.

Cutting tool: The cutting tool used is High Speed Steel (HSS). It was selected due to its high hardness (60-65 HRC), high wear resistance, high red hardness (retains hardness at high temperatures), good toughness and resistance to thermal shock. Its chemical compositions are: Tungsten (w): 12-18%, Molybdenum (Mo): 3-5%, Vanadium (V): 1-2%, Chromium (Cr): 3 – 5%, Carbon (C): 0.7 – 1.2%, Manganese (Mn): 0.5-1.5%, Silicon (Si): 0.5-1.5%, balance Fe [7].

Method

The workpiece (AISI 1045) steel was machined using HSS cutting tool. The general purpose Lathe machine was deployed for the turning operation. Table 1 presents the specifications of the Lathe machine, while Figure 1 portrays the Lathe machine during operation. The cutting parameters used are: Cutting speed (V_c): 50-200m/min, Feed rate (F): 0.2 – 0.5mm/rev. and depth of cut (DC): 1.4 – 1.8mm.

Table 1: Features of a General purpose Lathe Machine [8]

Swing over bed	200-400mm (7.9 – 15.7in)
Distance between centers	400-1000mm (15.7 – 39.4in)
Spindle bore	20-50mm (0.8-2in)
Spindle speed	50-2000 rpm
Power	2-10KW (2.7 – 13.4hp)
Accuracy	$\pm 0.01\text{mm}$ ($\pm 0.004\text{in}$)

Figure 1 - Turning Process

Data was collected over a period of 5 weeks between April and May, 2024 with an average of 4 projects carried out in a week. Design matrix was constructed by applying the Central Composite Design (CCD). This was adopted because of its reliability, time saving and efficiency when the effects of several operating conditions on the final output are considered by suggesting the minimum number of runs [9][10].

The software used is the design expert while the application used in the Response Surface Methodology (RSM). Eighteen (18) experimental runs were carried out at two levels.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the conducted experiments are presented as shown in Table 2, for all 18 experimental runs.

Table 2: Experimental Results

Run	A: Cutting Speed (m/min)	B: Feed Rate (mm/rev)	C: Depth of Cut (mm)	Cutting Force Fc (N)
1	190	0.5	1.65	264
2	150	0.3	1.8	235
3	190	0.4	1.4	195
4	150	0.5	1.8	232
5	230	0.3	1.5	231
6	190	0.4	1.65	232
7	150	0.3	1.5	169
8	150	0.5	1.5	237
9	190	0.4	1.65	258
10	190	0.4	1.65	231
11	230	0.3	1.8	239
12	150	0.4	1.65	204
13	230	0.5	1.5	232
14	190	0.4	1.65	231
15	190	0.2	1.65	212
16	190	0.4	1.5	235
17	250	0.4	1.65	237
18	190	0.4	1.65	248

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Quadratic model

Table 3 presents the ANOVA data

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis for the Cutting Force (F_c)

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	7100.42	9	788.94	5.57	0.0065	significant
A-Cutting Speed	1028.21	1	1028.21	7.26	0.0225	
B-Feed Rate	1613.72	1	1613.72	11.40	0.0071	
C-Depth of Cut	1399.96	1	1399.96	9.89	0.0104	
AB	595.12	1	595.12	4.20	0.0675	
AC	325.12	1	325.12	2.30	0.1607	
BC	741.13	1	741.13	5.23	0.0452	
A ²	550.86	1	550.86	3.89	0.0769	
B ²	0.0003	1	0.0003	2.149E-06	0.9989	
C ²	951.87	1	951.87	6.72	0.0268	
Residual	1416.13	10	141.61			
Lack of Fit	794.63	5	158.93	1.28	0.3970	not significant
Pure Error	621.50	5	124.30			
Cor Total	8516.55	19				

The **Model F-value** of 5.57 implies the model is significant. There is only a 0.65% chance that an F-value this large could occur due to noise.

P-values less than 0.0500 indicate model terms are significant [11]. In this case A, B, C, BC, C² are significant model terms. Values greater than 0.1000 indicate the model terms are not significant. If there are many insignificant model terms (not counting those required to support hierarchy), model reduction may improve your model.

The **Lack of Fit F-value** of 1.28 implies that the Lack of Fit is not significant relative to the pure error. There is a 39.70% chance that a Lack of Fit F-value this large could occur due to noise. Non-significant lack of fit is good we want the model to fit. The fit statistics is displayed in Table 4.

Table 4: Fit Statistics

Std. Dev.	11.90	R ²	0.8337
Mean	229.65	Adjusted R²	0.6891
C.V. %	5.18	Predicted R²	0.0888
		Adeq Precision	10.3268

The **Predicted R²** of 0.0888 is not as close to the **Adjusted R²** of 0.6891 as is normally expected; i.e. the difference is less than 0.2. This indicate that the model is ideal and there's no need for model reduction, response transformation, outliers, etc.

Adeq Precision measures the signal to noise ratio. A ratio greater than 4 is desirable [1]. Your ratio of 10.327 indicates an adequate signal. This model can be used to navigate the design space.

Estimation of Coefficient of Cutting Force Parameters

The cutting force model is developed based on the regression output, where the dependent variable is the force and the independent variables are cutting speed, depth of cut and feed rate. Given that cutting force depends on these cutting parameters spindle speed (S), feed rate (F), and depth of cut (D), the cutting force model is obtained as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Coefficients in Terms of Coded Factors

Factor	Coefficient Estimate	df	Standard Error	95% CI		VIF
				Low	High	
Intercept	239.42	1	4.85	228.60	250.23	
A-Cutting Speed	8.68	1	3.22	1.50	15.85	1.0000
B-Feed Rate	10.87	1	3.22	3.70	18.05	1.0000
C-Depth of Cut	10.12	1	3.22	2.95	17.30	1.0000
AB	-8.62	1	4.21	-18.00	0.7495	1.0000
AC	-6.38	1	4.21	-15.75	3.00	1.0000
BC	-9.63	1	4.21	-19.00	-0.2505	1.0000
A ²	-6.18	1	3.13	-13.17	0.8020	1.02
B ²	0.0046	1	3.13	-6.98	6.99	1.02
C ²	-8.13	1	3.13	-15.11	-1.14	1.02

The coefficient estimate represents the expected change in response per unit change in factor value when all remaining factors are held constant. The intercept in an orthogonal design is the overall average response of all the runs. The coefficients are adjustments around that average based on the factor settings. When the factors are orthogonal the VIFs are 1; VIFs greater than 1 indicate multi-collinearity, the higher the VIF the more severe the correlation of factors. As a rough rule, VIFs less than 10 are tolerable [12].

Final Equation in Terms of Coded Factors

$$F_c = +239.42 + 8.68A + 10.87B + 10.12C - 8.62AB - 6.38AC - 9.63BC - 6.18A^2 + 0.459B^2 - 8.13C^2 \quad (1.0)$$

Where:

- F_c = Cutting Force (dependent variable)
- A = Spindle speed (independent variable)
- B = Feed rate (independent variable)
- C = Depth of cut (independent variable)

The Equation (1.0) in terms of coded factors can be used to make predictions about the response for given levels of each factor. By default, the high levels of the factors are coded as +1 and the low levels are coded as -1. The coded equation is useful for identifying the relative impact of the factors by comparing the factor coefficients.

Final Equation in Terms of Actual Factors

Cutting Force

$$\begin{aligned} = & -1999.923 + 4.301 \text{ Cutting speed} + 1576.772 \text{ Feed Rate} + 1718.019 \text{ Depth of cut} \\ & - 2.156 \text{ Cutting speed} * \text{Feed rate} - 1.063 \text{ Cutting speed} * \text{Depth of cut} \\ & - 641.667 \text{ Feed rate} * \text{Depth of cut} - 0.004 \text{ Cutting speed}^2 + 0.459 \text{ Feed rate}^2 \\ & - 361.206 \text{ Depth of cut}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.0)$$

The Equation (2.0) in terms of actual factors can be used to make predictions about the response for given levels of each factor. Here, the levels should be specified in the original units for each factor. This equation should not be used to determine the relative impact of each factor because the coefficients are scaled to accommodate the units of each factor and the intercept is not at the center of the design space.

Accuracy of the Model

An analysis is made between the experimentally obtained results, and that obtained from the mathematical model. The result obtained, is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Report of comparison between experimental and predicted values of the cutting force

Run Order	Actual Value	Predicted Value	Residual	Leverage	Internally Studentized Residuals	Externally Studentized Residuals	Cook's Distance	Influence on Fitted Value DFFITS
1	264.00	257.71	6.29	0.607	0.843	0.830	0.110	1.032
2	235.00	223.07	11.93	0.670	1.745	1.985	0.618	2.827 ⁽¹⁾
3	195.00	199.40	-4.40	0.607	-0.590	-0.570	0.054	-0.709
4	232.00	242.81	-10.81	0.670	-1.580	-1.731	0.506	-2.465 ⁽¹⁾
5	231.00	218.17	12.83	0.670	1.876	2.211	0.714	3.149 ⁽¹⁾
6	232.00	239.42	-7.42	0.166	-0.683	-0.663	0.009	-0.296
7	169.00	170.82	-1.82	0.670	-0.266	-0.253	0.014	-0.360
8	237.00	229.06	7.94	0.670	1.162	1.185	0.274	1.687
9	258.00	239.42	18.58	0.166	1.710	1.929	0.058	0.862
10	231.00	239.42	-8.42	0.166	-0.775	-0.758	0.012	-0.339
11	239.00	244.92	-5.92	0.670	-0.866	-0.854	0.152	-1.216
12	204.00	207.34	-3.34	0.607	-0.448	-0.429	0.031	-0.534
13	232.00	241.91	-9.91	0.670	-1.449	-1.547	0.426	-2.203 ⁽¹⁾
14	231.00	239.42	-8.42	0.166	-0.775	-0.758	0.012	-0.339
15	212.00	221.15	-9.15	0.607	-1.227	-1.263	0.233	-1.571
16	235.00	233.46	1.54	0.607	0.207	0.196	0.007	0.244
17	237.00	236.52	0.4761	0.607	0.064	0.061	0.001	0.075
18	248.00	239.42	8.58	0.166	0.790	0.774	0.012	0.346

In comparing results between the experiment and predicted values, a graph of predicted and actual values using the mathematical model is shown in Figure 2.

The graph shows that the errors are uniformly distributed. This validates the strength of the model in predicting the result.

Figure 2: Plot of Experimental vs Predicted Values of the Responses

3D PLOTS

Three Dimensional plots have been provided, to further help analysis the effect of the process parameters on the response. Figure 3 – 5 presents three different combination of the process parameters against the response.

Figure 3: Plot of the Cutting Force against the Depth of Cut and Cutting Speed

This plot (Figure 3) explains the relationship between the depth of cut (mm) and the cutting speed (m/min) and their effect on the cutting force (N).

It can be seen that from their lowest point (starting point) of 1.5(mm) and 150(m/min) the commensurable cutting force is very low but as both parameters are increased, the cutting force begins to rise. This rise in cutting force gets to an optimum force and thus maintains a constant rate. This rate is maintained for a period and then the cutting force begins to decrease or decline.

This implies that both parameters have great influence on the cutting force and they are favourable to the cutting force but only to a particular point. After that point, if they are further increased the cutting force is bound to decrease.

Figure 4: Plot of the Cutting Force against the Feed Rate and Cutting Speed

This plot (Figure 4) explains the relationship between the feed rate (min/rev) and cutting speed (m/min) and their effect on the cutting force.

It can be seen that from their lowest point (starting point) of 0.3(mm/rev) and 150(m/min) the commensurable cutting force is very low but as both parameters are increased, the cutting force begins to rise. This rise in cutting force gets to an optimum force and thus maintains a constant rate. This rate is maintained for a period and then the cutting force begins to decrease or decline.

This implies that both parameters have great influence on the cutting force and they are favourable to the cutting force but only to a particular point. After that point, if they are further increased the cutting force is bound to decrease.

Factor Coding: Actual

3D Surface

Cutting Force Fc (N)

Design Points:

● Above Surface

○ Below Surface

169 264

X1 = B

X2 = C

Actual Factor

A = 190

Figure 5: Plot of the Cutting Force against the Depth of Cut and Feed Rate

This plot (Figure 5) explains the relationship between the depth of cut (mm) and the feed rate (mm/rev) and their effect on the cutting force.

It can be seen that from their lowest point (starting point) of 1.5(mm) and 0.3(min/rev) the commensurable cutting force is very low but as both parameters are increased, the cutting force begins to rise. This rise in cutting force gets to an optimum force and thus maintains a constant rate. This rate is maintained for a period and then the cutting force begins to decrease or decline.

This implies that both parameters have great influence on the cutting force and they are favourable to the cutting force but only to a particular point. After that point, if they are further increased the cutting force is bound to decrease.

Numerical Optimization

Table 7: Numerical Optimization of the Variables

NUMBER	CUTTING SPEED	FEED RATE	DEPTH OF CUT	CUTTING FORCE FC	DESIRABILITY	
1	155.247	0.462	1.738	241.548	1.000	Selected
2	150.000	0.300	1.500	170.816	1.000	
3	230.000	0.500	1.800	230.160	1.000	
4	150.000	0.500	1.500	229.057	1.000	
5	230.000	0.300	1.500	218.170	1.000	
6	230.000	0.300	1.800	244.919	1.000	
7	150.000	0.500	1.800	242.806	1.000	
8	150.000	0.300	1.800	223.066	1.000	
9	230.000	0.500	1.500	241.910	1.000	
10	169.322	0.317	1.662	222.201	1.000	
11	224.046	0.394	1.722	242.773	1.000	
12	206.079	0.462	1.553	242.077	1.000	
13	178.940	0.384	1.549	221.616	1.000	
14	178.948	0.429	1.694	242.389	1.000	
15	160.631	0.329	1.541	197.460	1.000	
16	225.725	0.488	1.614	245.538	1.000	

Table 7 shows results of numerical optimization carried out to determine the optimal solution for the machining parameters. From the results obtained, a combined process parameter of 155.25m/min cutting speed, Feed rate of 0.46mm/rev, and depth of cut of 1.74mm is obtained at a cutting force value of 241.55N.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research work developed an empirical model for predicting cutting force in turning processes. It also identified key factors influencing cutting force coefficients and cutting parameters.

Finally, it demonstrated the effectiveness of Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to validate the model. Hence, the developed model could be applied in the manufacturing industry during machining (turning) operations.

From the results obtained, an optimal cutting force of 241.5N was obtained at a combined process parameter of 155.25m/min cutting speed, Feed rate of 0.46mm/rev, and depth of cut of 1.74mm respectively.

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